

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *This article discusses the importance of innovation for the present-day development and progress of Uzbekistan's economy, highlighting the benefits of financing innovative projects.*

Key words: *innovation, modernization, infrastructure, credit, investment, bank, percent, resource, discovery, financing.*

In his address to the Oliy Majlis, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized the need for updated management systems in the economy, timely introduction of effective mechanisms to support innovative ideas, and identified them as significant challenges [1]. Furthermore, he identified technological backwardness, lack of resource and energy-saving technologies, and slow implementation of alternative energy sources as obstacles hindering economic development.

To enhance the competitiveness of the national economy and penetrate global markets, consistent economic reforms are necessary. This entails fostering the rapid development of new enterprises and production sectors based on advanced technologies. In essence, economic competitiveness cannot be achieved without the advancement of innovative activities. By definition, innovation refers to the acceptance and public recognition of new discoveries, events, services, and methods. Introducing innovation involves the process of applying these new advancements, and from that point forward, the adopted improvements become innovations.

Hence, the ultimate goal of implementing innovation is to yield positive outcomes. Consequently, innovation is closely tied to the field of investment. In the context of national economic development, the following areas can be identified as priority domains for innovation and investment activities:

- Modernizing enterprises and expediting technical and technological upgrades, accompanied by the widespread adoption of modern and flexible technologies.

- Implementing specific measures to enhance the competitiveness of export-oriented enterprises in foreign markets and fostering additional factors that promote exports.

- Boosting the competitiveness of enterprises in the real sector by incentivizing the reduction of production costs and overall product expenses.

- Implementation of measures to modernize the electric power system, reduce energy consumption, and introduce an efficient energy-saving system.

- Supporting local producers by stimulating demand in the domestic market.

Undoubtedly, the role of innovations in modernizing the national economy and enhancing its competitiveness is unparalleled. However, certain conditions must be fulfilled for the organization and development of innovation activities in the country [2]:

- State innovation policy: developing and defining the goals of the country's innovation strategy and establishing mechanisms to support priority innovation programs and projects by the state authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

- Investment potential: the cumulative resources of the state, industries, enterprises, and organizations in various forms (including material, financial, intellectual, scientific, technical, economic, etc.).

- Innovation field: the areas of activity involving producers and consumers of innovative products (work, services), encompassing the creation and dissemination of innovations.

- Innovation infrastructure: various institutions that facilitate and influence the implementation of innovation activities.

- Innovation program (at the enterprise, industry, territory, state, region, and interstate levels): encompassing the allocation of resources, responsible parties, and deadlines for innovation projects, ensuring the effective accomplishment of objectives related to the development and deployment of new product types and a range of innovative projects and events.

There are several types of innovation project financing. The primary method is funding based on the project's creditworthiness, the participants' ability to sustain themselves without considering guarantees from third parties for loan repayment. Another form of investment financing can be viewed as a source for debt repayment. This type of financing, the third category, relies on cash flows

generated from project implementation and enterprise assets as loan collateral. The fourth type of project financing is based on the economic and technical viability of the enterprise [3].

We acknowledge that the effective implementation of innovation projects is crucial in reducing product costs in economic sectors, enhancing labor productivity, improving product quality, and ensuring the overall competitiveness of the economy.

In global practice, project financing often refers to a type of financing arrangement where the proceeds from the project's sale serve as the sole source of debt repayment. However, the interpretation of the term "project financing" varies across countries. For instance, in the United States, it is understood that financing is primarily organized using the founder's personal funds, with the income from the project's sale being the sole means of debt repayment.

In Europe, the term encompasses different options and methods for providing financial resources required for project implementation. Subsequently, "project financing" refers to a system of financial and commercial operations involving loans from banks, budgetary support, assistance from various state organizations, investment funds, insurance companies, and other interested investors [1]

The interconnectedness between Uzbekistan's economic situation and innovation can be observed in several main aspects. Firstly, innovation activity impacts the overall national economy, serving as its material foundation. Secondly, it can be analyzed as a distinct market entity to evaluate its influence on specific enterprises. Lastly, the socio-economic outcomes of implementing innovation policies are studied.

Amidst the ongoing modernization of Uzbekistan's economy, innovations are crucial for sustainable growth. Investing in new technologies facilitates the production of competitive consumer goods with high demand.

The innovation policy serves as a significant instrument for influencing the country's economy and the business activities of economic entities. It is considered a vital component of the state's economic policy, enabling direct influence on production rates, acceleration of scientific and technological progress, changes in the structure of social production, and the resolution of social issues.

In conclusion, let's briefly highlight a number of key activities and measures for the establishment and further development of an

innovative economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan: [Remaining part of the text is missing, please provide the missing content.]

- To study all the technological knowledge and innovations needed from developed countries and gradually apply them to the branches of the republic's economy, taking into account our national interests.

- The attraction of investors and foreign capital to domestic innovative projects is of paramount importance.

- Organizing a knowledge base dedicated to technological innovations and making it accessible to all citizens through an Internet portal.

- Developing innovation and ensuring the reliable protection of intellectual property to transform achievements in this field into high-value-added products.

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